

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP4

Grid planning and operation strategies

Deliverable D4.6

Feasibility study of MVDC Hybrid Grids for large scale research facilities

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List of Abbreviations

IT	Information Technology
PV	Photovoltaic
AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
MV	medium voltage
LV	low voltage
MVDC	Medium Voltage Direct Current
MVAC	Medium Voltage Alternating Current
LVDC	Low Voltage Direct Current
IGBT	Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor
DAB3	three-phase dual-active bridge
3LNPC	three-level neutral-point-clamped converter
AFE	Active Front End
RMS	root-mean-square

Executive Summary

At the RWTH-Aachen University a new Campus West will be built. This Campus area includes a thermal network as well as an IT-center, PV power plants and charging stations for electric vehicles. It is considered to connect these components using a customer owned medium voltage grid, in order to maximise self consumption. Within this deliverable, a study is implemented based on the plans for Campus West, which identifies the advantages of using a Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) grid configuration compared to a 10 kV Alternating Current (AC) reference grid for that purpose. Parameters considered in this analysis are different voltage levels, transformer efficiency, converter efficiency and cable transmission losses. The aim of this study is to identify the key influencing factors along with the conditions that result in the MVDC grid configuration being more feasible than the AC reference scenario.

In order to carry out the comparison between AC and Direct Current (DC) systems, grid systems are first designed accordingly for the use of the respective technology.

Within the scope of the comparison, both monopolar and bipolar DC system configurations are compared with the AC reference scenario.

For the three-level neutral-point-clamped converter (3LNPC) and the modular three-phase dual-active bridge (DAB3) the efficiency curves are calculated by means of simulation.

In order to compare the efficiency of the concepts, the power flows for a whole year are calculated in hourly resolution based on the load profiles, including the resulting losses in the converters, transformers and cables. The results show the following:

1. DC power transmission is advantageous for voltage levels $U_{DC} \geq 5$ kV compared to the 10 kV AC reference scenario.
2. Considering material consumption as well as efficiency allows to identify monopolar grid structures as more advantageous, since they only need two conductors instead of three.
3. While designing the DC-DC converter, it is financially rewarding to oversize the converters instead of sizing them only for the maximum power needed, if the load profile is constant. Hence, a more efficient operating point can be achieved.
4. If the efficiency of the MVDC-LVDC converter is 1.7 % higher than the efficiency of the active rectifier used in the AC reference scenario, the implementation of a MVDC grid is potentially more feasible.
5. The losses in the MVDC-MVAC substations exceed the losses in the MVAC-MVAC substation by far, because of the additional converter needed for rectification in the DC scenarios.
6. Distributing the power supply evenly among the active substations using power-flow control does not make the substations more efficient, even though it allows to design the components for smaller nominal power values. However, distributing the power supply leads in this example to higher cable transmission losses.
7. Increasing the cable transmission distances by a factor of ten leads to the DC systems being more efficient than the AC-reference system. Especially for monopolar configurations with grid voltages $U_{DC} \geq 12$ kV.

Limitations and critical review of this analysis:

1. As the case study includes a consumer that withdraws constantly a high amount of power, it could be that the application of the results to other use cases needs to be critically

evaluated, especially concerning the derivation of more generalised conclusions.

2. The comparison of the cable transmission losses is based on the assumption that the current densities that can be realised without exceeding the thermal limits of the cable are the same for AC and DC transmission.

In the context of this case study different parameters have been identified, that lead to better feasibility of a DC-grid, compared to the AC reference grid scenario. While the impact of the cable transmission losses is comparably low and only becomes relevant when the transmission length is increased, the key influencing factor is the efficiency of the converters used in the grid systems. DC grid scenarios become potentially feasible after nine years or more, if the DC-DC converters connecting the MVDC grid to the LVDC grids have a maximum efficiency that exceeds the efficiency of the active rectifiers in the AC reference scenario by 1.7 %. Also, for the use case investigated in this case study, the efficiency of the MV Active Front End (AFE) was identified to have significant impact on the overall system efficiency.

Future work should further investigate the modelling of converter efficiency, in order to obtain results that can further differentiate between different types of semiconductor switches or types of converter control. In addition, further consideration should be given to the aspect of material consumption by determining tolerable current densities in DC cable configurations and comparing the material consumption of the medium frequency transformers and 50 Hz transformers implemented in different DC and AC grid configurations.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

The activities and contributions of Task T4.6 "Case Study" are described and reported in this document. According to the Description of Action (DoA) a short study is implemented to identify the advantages of MVDC supply for a new university campus area and to provide a basis for DC grid planning. In this context a state-of-the art AC grid is compared to a meshed DC grid.

At the RWTH-Aachen University a new Campus West will be built. This campus area includes a thermal network as well as an Information Technology (IT) center, Photovoltaic (PV) power plants and charging stations for electric vehicles. It is considered to connect these components using a privately operated medium voltage grid, in order to maximise self consumption. Within this deliverable, a study is implemented based on the plans for Campus West, which identifies the advantages of using a MVDC grid configuration compared to a 10 kV AC reference grid for that purpose.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content whereas Section 2 introduces the case study that serves as basis for the work carried out in the context of Task T4.6 and some general advantages of DC-technology. Next, the approach to design the different AC and DC grid configurations is explained in Section 3. In Section 4 the results are presented and discussed. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5.

2 Campus West Grid Structure

2.1 Campus West Areal

In 2018 the RWTH Aachen University purchased an area next to the train station in the west of Aachen. There, the RWTH Aachen University plans to construct a new area for its university campus referred to as "Campus West". In advance of planning, studies regarding possible strategies for the energy supply of this area have been conducted. Apart from a concept for heating and cooling supply via a thermal network, also load profiles for power generation via photovoltaic (PV) plants and power consumption of different consumers in the area have been developed. Based on those load profiles, different grid operation strategies for a university owned medium voltage AC grid have been investigated (Monti, 2020), (Müller, 2020).

In the following the basic grid structure and load profiles of the main consumers and generators are briefly presented.

Figure 1 depicts the basic structure of the electrical medium voltage grid which connects the main power consumers and power generators in the area. It is assumed that this grid is implemented as a customer plant. While the thermal network supplies all buildings within the Campus West area, the medium voltage grid is planned to connect specific buildings only, in order to maximise the utilisation of power generated by renewable energy sources. The medium voltage grid comprises the IT-center of the University, as well as the energy center, where heating and cooling are provided by reversible heat-pumps, for the thermal network. Via the grid, these main consumers are connected to four car park buildings. Those provide charging stations for electric vehicles and have photovoltaic panels installed on their rooftops and outside walls, enabling them to feed surplus power into the grid. Hence, whenever the power generation exceeds the power consumption of the charging stations, the excess power can be used to supply the IT-center and the energy center. Also included in this figure are possible locations for substations, denoted with "Sub1", "Sub2" and "Sub3". They connect the private medium voltage grid to the public grid in order to supply the residual load.

In Figure 2 examples of the courses throughout one year of consumption and generation for the IT-center, the energy center and a car park building can be found. As can be seen from Figure 2, it is assumed that the IT-center is a constant load. The heat-pumps in the energy center need ca. 100 kW during winter time and during summertime up to 1.6 MW to provide enough cooling to the thermal network. The charging stations offer charging points with different power rates and technologies. The charging infrastructure comprises 11 kW and 22 kW AC charging as well as 50 kW DC charging. The power distribution of the different charging stations is derived from the characteristics of the existing charging infrastructure in Aachen using the platform "Chargemap" (*Chargemap SaS: "Chargemap"*, 2022). The number of charging stations in the car parks as well as the surface available for PV generation was determined depending on their surface and rooftop area. The charging behaviour of car park users has been modelled and load profiles were derived in (Monti, 2020). Assuming that the PV generation can be used to supply the charging power, the load and generation profiles of every car park are combined and the residual load curve in Figure 2 results.

Figure 1: Basic Grid Structure.

Figure 2: Load profiles over the course of one year for the IT-center (ITC), the energy-center (EC) and one car park building (P1) according to (Monti, 2020).

2.2 Potential Advantages of DC Technology

DC technology has many advantages compared to the established AC technology, some of which are listed below (De Doncker, 2014). DC technology has already proven to be advantageous in the high voltage sector and is a well established technology for high voltage power transmission systems. Furthermore, an increasing number of DC projects on the low voltage level has been realised in recent years. One prominent example in Germany is the project DC-Industrie (ZVEI e.V., 2022), with a LVDC microgrid demonstrated for industrial applications. In the Netherlands there are also projects that install LVDC infrastructure in public buildings (DC-Systems, 2022). This deliverable seeks to examine, to what extent the advantages that

DC-technology has compared to AC-technology, lead to increased feasibility of DC systems in medium voltage applications. Therefore, a comparison between several DC systems of different voltage levels and an AC reference system is conducted as a case study using a customer owned electricity grid as example application. The advantages listed below will also be the evaluation criteria applied for this comparison.

1. increased efficiency due to absence of reactive current,
2. decreased material consumption,
3. better power-flow control.

In the following this report presents an analysis of efficiency of MVDC grid concepts on different voltage levels.

Figure 3: Overview of AC system.

Figure 4: Overview of DC system.

3 MVDC-grid scenarios

In this section simulation models of the medium voltage electricity grid for Campus West are developed. There are two different setups. The setup for the medium voltage AC grid is shown in Figure 3, while Figure 4 depicts the diagram that serves as foundation for the analysis of different MVDC grid scenarios. In Figure 4, as an example, two substations supply the MVDC grid. Each substation consists of one 50 Hz transformer and a rectifier unit. The number of substations actively supplying power to the medium voltage DC grid ranges from one to three. The amount of power provided by each substations varies depending on the number of active substations and the application of power flow control. Arriving on the MVDC side of the setup, different voltage levels and monopolar as well as bipolar grid configurations are investigated. It is assumed that in the car parks, the energy center and the IT-center, there is already an LVDC grid infrastructure in place. The medium voltage and low voltage DC grids are connected by DC-DC converters, which are also included in the analysis.

The AC grid setup shown in Figure 3 serves as the reference scenario which is used as benchmark for the simulation results of the DC scenarios. In the AC setup, the medium voltage AC grid is supplied via one substation which consists of a 50 Hz transformer. The root-mean-square (RMS) value of the nominal line-to-line voltage is 10 kV AC. The LVDC infrastructure in the buildings is connected to the MVAC grid via a 50 Hz transformer and a rectifier unit.

3.1 DC Circuit Breakers and Voltage Levels

There are several possible protection concepts for DC grid systems. So far, no concept has been finally standardised. A currently promising concept, analogous to AC protection technology, is to use circuit breakers that can interrupt a fault current. With DC technology, however,

Figure 5: Pole-to-pole fault current with a distance of 0.5 km from converter to fault location and varying parameters (Qawasmi, 2021).

there is the problem that there is no natural current zero crossing, which is used with AC circuit breakers to extinguish the fault current. In addition, wired DC grids driven by active inverters and DC-DC converters are highly capacitive. This can lead to very high short-circuit currents in the event of a fault, which are characterised by a very short rise time. Figure 5 illustrates an example of a DC short-circuit current during a pole-to-pole fault in a bipolar medium voltage DC-grid with a nominal voltage of $U_{DC} = 2.5$ kV. The fault occurs in the middle of the transmission path between two converters at a distance $d = 0.5$ km from each converter. Figure 5a shows that the maximum amplitude value of the fault current and the rise time of the current increase with increasing connected capacitance C_{out} . The maximum amplitude of the fault current is also highly dependent on the nominal grid voltage, as is demonstrated in Figure 5b.

This situation results in high requirements for DC circuit breakers. Besides pure semiconductor based concepts there are hybrid concepts consisting of an electrical and a mechanical part. Purely mechanical switches are not suitable for reliably disconnecting the fault current.

In the field of railway technology, active DC systems up to 3 kV are realised and operated, which also have circuit breakers. Hence, for voltages up to 3 kV DC circuit breakers already exist and are available on the market. For this application, current limiting high speed circuit breakers with arc chambers are implemented, such as (Sécheron SA, 2021) or (ABB Industrial Solutions, 2020). As the technological readiness level of MVDC circuit breakers is a bottleneck for the realisation of MVDC grids, in the beginning of this analysis, it was in question whether in the feasibility comparison only DC voltage levels should be considered for which the circuit breakers are already available. However, these circuit breakers are designed to operate in catenary networks and are characterised by inadequate properties. Hence, the design of these circuit breakers can only be used to a limited extent for capacitive DC grids. Figure 6 illustrates the relationship between the time t_i the breaker needs to detect the over current and initiate the fault current interruption, and the initial rate of current rise for different breaker types. The graph distinguishes between breakers designed for a constant current of 2.6 kA (UR26) and for 3.6 kA (UR36), 4.0 kA (UR40) and 4.6 kA (UR46). It can be seen, that t_i decreases with increasing steepness of the current rise. In the example marked by the red line in Figure 6 the breaker would need approximately 4.3 ms at a current rise rate of $3 \times 10^6 \frac{A}{s}$ to start to open the connectors. The graph also shows that the minimum detection time for both breaker types is circa $t_{i,min} = 2$ ms.

In addition to $t_{i,min}$, the actuation mechanism needs then 15 to 30 milliseconds to open the

Figure 6: Amount of time t_f that is needed for the circuit breaker to detect the short circuit current depending on the current rate in $\frac{A}{s}$ (Sécheron SA, 2021).

Figure 7: Grid configuration used to calculate the short circuit rise time and the peak current value at the fault location. Fault location is inserted as additional node in the graph.

breaker completely (Sécheron SA, 2021). With regards to the example depicted in Figure 5 it becomes clear that the breaker from the data sheet does not operate fast enough to interrupt the depicted example fault current before it reaches its maximum value. Moreover, it is not even sure, if the overcurrent would be detected before the fault current starts to decrease again. It can be concluded, that circuit breakers that are available on the market, are not suitable to protect a MVDC grid from the short circuit peak current. This applies in particular to MVDC grids with higher output capacitances and shorter transmission paths between the grid nodes, than in the example.

Therefore, the availability of DC circuit breakers for lower voltage levels is not a justification to exclude higher DC grid voltages from consideration in the analysis.

Moreover, Figure 5 and Figure 6 demonstrate the necessity to develop circuit breakers capable of higher voltages and faster interruption times.

Such as the hybrid circuit breaker developed by SCiBreak AB in this project, which incorporates the voltage-source-converter assisted resonant current (VARC) technology concept and a Thompson coil actuator. This technology allowed during a test in 2018 for a time span between fault occurrence and current interruption of $t_{i,SciBreak} = 0.4$ ms at a voltage level of 40 kV and a total interruption time of 2.8 ms (SCiBreak, 2022). Within the project prototypes for 5 kV and for 14 kV are developed.

To estimate the short circuit current rise time and its peak current value, the calculation method of (Li et al., 2017) is applied as an example to the DC grid configuration at Campus West, depicted in Figure 7. Therefore, the fault location is inserted as additional node into the graph, as illustrated in the example in Figure 8a. As stated by the authors of (Li et al., 2017), the calculation method is only valid to calculate the course of the fault current until its peak value is reached. Figure 8b depicts the time period for which the calculation is accurate. This can also be explained by looking at the voltage waveforms in Figure 9b. During the fault all voltages at the output capacitances of the converters $uc1 \dots uc9$ decline during the fault. But at $t \approx 0.8$ ms the voltage at node 2 (Sub2) becomes negative. Output capacitors of converters are usually protected against reversal of polarity, which is not considered by the calculation method proposed in (Li et al., 2017). Hence, the results calculated for $t \geq 0.8$ ms are not accurate anymore. However, as the peak current value is reached at $t = 0.45$ ms, the results from the calculation method until then can be used as a first estimation. The parameters used for this calculation are listed in Table 2 and Table 1 lists information regarding the distances between the nodes. In the table, the numbers in the first line labelled with "Branch" refer to the node numbers depicted in Figure 7. The short circuit in the grid represented by the graph in Figure 7 at the example location at node 11 in the middle of node 3 (Sub3) and node 10 causes a peak fault current of $I_{fault,max} = 25.65$ kA at $t = 0.45$ ms. This results in a current rate of approximately $di/dt = 57$ kA/ms, which is illustrated by Figure 9c. Under these circumstances the hybrid circuit breaker technology would not be suitable. In order to make the hybrid circuit breaker technology feasible for the exemplary fault situation at Campus West, the current rise can be limited by adding inductance to the cable transmission lines. In the diagrams depicted in Figure 10 the inductance in every branch is increased by 0.5 mH, except for the branches connected to the fault location at node 11. There, the inductance is increased by 0.25 mH, as it is assumed, that the additional inductors are integrated before the fault occurs. A comparison of the inductance values before and after the increase is listed in Table 1. As can be seen from Figure 10a, the maximum peak value of the fault current, as well as the current increase rate decline when the inductance in each branch is increased. The new maximum value is $I_{fault,max,new} = 13.83$ kA at $t = 1$ ms. With the lower increase rate of $di/dt = 13.83$ kA/ms the properties of the SCiBreak circuit breaker could suffice, as the

Table 1: Distances between the graph nodes per branch and resulting inductance values of the designated branches before and after the increase.

Branch	1-8	8-9	9-4	4-5	5-6	6-10	2-10	3-10	3-7	3-11	10-11
[km]	0.353	0.056	0.076	0.051	0.166	0.382	0.291	0.227	0.09	0.113	0.114
L [mH]	0.106	0.017	0.023	0.015	0.05	0.115	0.087	0.068	0.027	0.034	0.034
L_{new} [mH]	0.606	0.517	0.523	0.515	0.55	0.615	0.587	0.568	0.527	0.284	0.284

Figure 8: Insertion of fault location into the graph and time span in which accurate results can be obtained with the calculation method proposed (Li et al., 2017).

time needed to build up the current through the resonance circuit as described in (SCiBreak, 2022) will take approximately 0.4 ms, which is circa 40 % of the total fault current rise time. Considering a time span of up to 100 μ s for fault detection this would mean, that the fault interruption could start after 0.5 ms at approximately 11 kA. An increase of cable inductance could be achieved by integrating inductors with an inductance of approximately the difference between the values in the second and third line of Table 1 at the beginning or the end of the branches.

Concluding, the design framework for the considered DC networks in the voltage range is kept in the study to a maximum of ± 8 kV, since it is assumed that in the near future products for this type of protection concept will be available.

3.2 Grid Configuration Design Process

3.2.1 DC-DC Converters

To connect the MVDC grid to the Low Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) side, a modular three-phase dual active bridge (DAB3) topology is chosen. The converter consists of several identical three-phase dual-active bridges in input-series-output-parallel connection. Figure 11 depicts an example of this configuration. To determine the efficiency of this converter topology, a simulation model based on (Joebges, 2021) was implemented. The simulated converter consists of

(a) Calculated current waveform for $U_{DC} = 5$ kV

(b) Calculated voltage waveform for $U_{DC} = 5$ kV

(c) Resulting fault current at fault location with $U_{DC} = 5$ kV

Figure 9: Calculated current and voltage waveforms.

Table 2: Parameters for the short circuit current calculation.

Parameter	Value	Comment
R	$0.1 \Omega/km$	Cable resistance, Al, 300 mm^2 (Südkabel GmbH, 2022)
R_C	$44 \mu\Omega$	Internal resistance of a 5 kV DC-link capacitor (Muecap, 2022)
L	0.3 mH/km	cable inductance, (Südkabel GmbH, 2022)
C	1 mF	Capacitance at the MVDC side of each converter
R_f	0.3Ω	Fault resistance, typical value (Qawasm, 2021)
L_C	50 nH	Parasitic inductance of the capacitor (Muecap, 2022)

(a) Calculated current waveform for $U_{DC} = 5$ kV and an increased cable inductance

(b) Calculated voltage waveform for $U_{DC} = 5$ kV and an increased cable inductance

(c) Resulting fault current at fault location with $U_{DC} = 5$ kV and an increased cable inductance

Figure 10: Calculated current and voltage waveforms.

Figure 11: Simplified circuit model of a modular DC-DC converter in input-series-output-parallel connection (Joebges, 2021).

Figure 12: Simplified circuit model of a three-phase dual active bridge converter (DAB3) (Joebges, 2021).

eight DAB3 modules and has a nominal power of 200 kW. On the high voltage side the voltage is $U_{in} = 5$ kV, while on the low voltage side, $U_{out} = 760$ V. As switching elements, Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor (IGBT) modules of Infineon, designed for a nominal collector-emitter voltage $V_{CES} = 1200$ V and a nominal current of $I_{nom} = 75$ A (Infineon Technologies AG, 2021), are used. The modules are operated at a switching frequency of $f_{sw} = 10$ kHz. The simplified equivalent circuit diagram of one DAB3-module is shown in Figure 12. The modules are operated with phase-shift modulation. This control scheme and other possible control strategies are explained in detail in the deliverable D3.11 of the HYPERRIDE project (Karsten & Hu, 2022). For the simulation, it is assumed that the voltage on the high voltage side, U_{in} , is equally distributed among the modules resulting in a module voltage on the primary side of $U_{pDC} = 625$ V. An equal distribution of the output current I_{out} among the modules on the output side is also assumed. In reality, power and voltage balancing between the modules are crucial for stable operation and can be achieved by implementing control strategies accordingly (Zumel, Ortega, Lazaro, Fernandez, & Barrado, 2013), (Joebges, 2021).

Figure 13 depicts the efficiency curve over the power, relative to the nominal power of the converter. The converter has a maximum efficiency of $\eta_{max} = 97.7\%$ at a power $P = 0.46P_{nom}$.

Figure 13: Efficiency curve of the modular three-phase dual-active-bridge converter related to operating points relative to nominal power.

Figure 14: Recommended current densities in aluminium cables according to (VDE, DIN, 2018), max. allowed cable temperature of 90°C, temperature of surrounding earth 20°C, three single-core cables bundled in a triangle, three-phase AC-system.

3.2.2 Cable Configurations

The cable-parameters are chosen as follows. From the load profiles, the maximum power demand of Campus West is identified. For this maximum power demand situation, the load-flow algorithm presented in (Beerten & Belmans, 2015) is run and outputs the maximum load current that will occur in the network. Considering the current capabilities of cables with different cross sections according to (VDE, DIN, 2018) a fitting cross section for this maximum current is chosen. Figure 14 illustrates the recommended current densities in aluminium cables for a maximum conductor temperature of 90°C, while assuming a temperature of 20°C for the surrounding earth. The cable resistance values are updated according to the selected cross section and the load-flow algorithm is reiterated, checking if thresholds for node voltages are exceeded or not.

The values in Figure 14 refer to three-phase AC-systems, laid as three single-core cables bundled in a triangle and equally loaded. In DC systems, there are either single forward and return conductors in monopolar grid configurations, or two conductors, for positive and negative pole respectively, and one as neutral conductor in bipolar grid configurations. Hence, in DC systems, the load is predominantly distributed among two conductors. Therefore, it is assumed that the current density values from (VDE, DIN, 2018) can be used as worst-case assessment.

3.2.3 AC-DC Connection

Every connection point from the public AC grid to the DC grid consists of a 50Hz transformer and an active front end. The size of the transformer is chosen according to the size categories presented in the ecological design regulations of the European Commission (European Commission, 2014). The active front end is implemented as three-phase three-level-neutral-point-clamped (3LNPC) converter. Figure 15 depicts the simplified electric circuit diagram of this three-phase topology. In contrast to two-level topologies, this multilevel topology can create a third output voltage level of zero volt by providing a current path through its clamping diodes. Thus, it can provide grid current with reduced harmonic content. In addition, the power electronic switches can be designed for lower blocking voltage ratings. Moreover, this topology allows for voltage balancing in bipolar grid configurations. Because of the properties mentioned above, this topology was identified as suitable for the application. The simulation model, im-

Figure 15: Simplified electric circuit diagram of a three-phase neutral-point-clamped converter (3LNPC) (Karsten & Hu, 2022).

plemented to create the efficiency curve shown in Figure 16, is based on the active front end converter described in (Karsten & Hu, 2022). The AC-side voltage is $U_{AC} = 3.3$ kV and the DC link voltage is $U_{DC} = 5$ kV. The switching frequency is chosen as $f_{sw} = 1$ kHz. As can be seen from Figure 16, the maximum efficiency is $\eta_{max} = 98.5\%$ at a power $P = 0.1P_{nom}$. Figure 17 shows the efficiencies of 50 Hz transformers with different nominal powers. According to the figure, the maximum efficiency increases with increasing rated power. If the efficiency curves from Figure 17 are considered in relation to their respective maximum value, Figure 18 results. Figure 18 shows that the efficiency profile for transformers of different rated powers is similar and the operation point of maximum efficiency seems to always be at $P = 0.4P_{nom}$. As the curve of the 1000 kVA transformer has the largest number of points, from (Siemens AG, 2016), this curve will serve as base for the transformer efficiencies considered in this analysis. The efficiency curves are scaled to the efficiency values required by (European Commission, 2014).

Figure 16: Efficiency curve of the three level neutral-point-clamped converter related to operating points relative to nominal power.

Figure 17: Efficiency curve of 50 Hz transformers for different nominal powers according to (Siemens AG, 2016).

Figure 18: Normed efficiency curves of 50 Hz transformers for different nominal powers.

4 Simulation Results

The load profiles available for this analysis describe the calculated power consumption and power generation over one year, with average values on an hourly basis. Based on the load profiles of the different consumers and generators in the Campus West area, first the losses of the medium voltage (MV) to low voltage (LV) conversion are calculated. Then, the resulting cable transmission losses are determined using either the DC power flow algorithm for the DC grids (Beerten, 2012), or the power flow calculation tool offered by matpower (R. D. Zimmerman, C. E. Murillo-Sanchez, 2020) for the AC reference scenario. The cable transmission losses and the converter and transformer losses have been calculated for the whole year.

4.1 MV-LV Interfaces

First, the losses in the MV-LV interfaces of the DC grid systems are compared to the losses that occur in the MV-LV interfaces of the reference AC-system. In the DC grid systems, the power demand is met by using different amounts of modular dual-active bridge converters, as described in Section 3, with a nominal power of 200 kW each. The number of converters in operation depends on the power that is withdrawn from or fed into the grid. If the power exceeds the nominal power of the active converters, another converter is set into operation, and the power transmitted is divided equally among them. It is assumed that the efficiency of the active converters corresponds to the efficiency curve depicted in Figure 13 for all grid voltages considered in this analysis. Table 3 gives an overview of the number of MV-LV converters used. To dimension the MVAC - LVDC connections for the MVAC scenario, power transformers of 630 kVA, 1000 kVA or 2000 kVA were selected. For the adjacent neutral-point-clamped converters, nominal power is assumed to correspond to the nominal power of the modular DAB3 converters. The peak efficiency of the transformers is determined according to the values presented in (European Commission, 2014). Figure 19 illustrates the losses occurring in the MV-LV converters and 50 Hz transformers over the course of one year for the MVAC reference case and the ± 5 kV DC grid configuration, exemplarily.

Figure 19 compares the energy losses occurring in the MVDC-LVDC converters in the DC system to the energy losses in the MVAC-LVAC connection points of the AC reference system. The energy losses in the DC-DC-converters add up to a total of $E_{loss, MVDC-LVDC} = 412$ MWh, while the energy losses in the 50 Hz transformers and the AFEs result in a slightly lower value of $E_{loss, MVAC-LVDC} = 406$ MWh. The difference in the total losses can essentially be attributed to the differences in the actual operating point efficiency of the converter units for the car parks. The car parks have a rather volatile load profile, as was mentioned in Section 2, and the converters predominantly operate at lower operating points. Since the 3LNPC model used in this analysis has a better partial load efficiency compared to the modular DAB3, the MVAC-LVDC connection of the car parks is here slightly more efficient. An overview of the nominal powers and average efficiencies of the MV-LV converter stations is depicted in Table 3.

The dimensioning of the DC-DC Converter for the IT-center, following the aforementioned process, would lead to a number of nine converters and a nominal power for power conversion of 1800 kW. The resulting average efficiency would be at 97,16 % and the energy losses over one year would accumulate to ca. 398 MWh. However, there is the possibility to add further converters to the MV-LV interface, in order to increase the nominal power and, assuming equal distribution of power among the converters, achieve an operation point at higher efficiency. The DC-DC converter has its peak efficiency of 97,7 % at 46 % of its nominal power (see Figure 13).

Figure 19: Losses occurring over the course of one year in the MV-LV interfaces of the ± 5 kV DC grid and the 10 kV AC grid.

As the power consumption of the IT-center is constant throughout the whole year, an increase of 0,54 % in efficiency has a noticeable effect on the power consumption reducing the annual loss energy to ca. 321 MWh. However, this would require to install a converter system for more than twice the nominal power that is actually needed, leading to higher investment costs. In order to evaluate the different design options and their impact on the efficiency of the MV-LV interface of the IT-center, the net present value method is applied according to Equation 1. In this equation, i represents the interest rate, z_t the income at point in time t , T is the total number of years that are considered for the evaluation and I represents the investment cost at the beginning of the time span ($t = 0$), while NPV is the net present value. The investment costs are calculated assuming a price of $150 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{kW}}$ and with regard to the investment cost $I_{P,base}$ of installing 1800 kW, which would be required in any case. To calculate the income, the energy losses that are saved because of the increase in efficiency are multiplied by the current electricity prices for industrial clients, which is at $40,05 \frac{\text{ct}}{\text{kWh}}$ (BDEW, 2022). The calculation of z_t is shown in Equation 2.

$$NPV = -(I_{P,new} - I_{P,base}) + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{z_t}{(1+i)^t} \quad (1)$$

$$z_t = (E_{\text{loss,base}} - E_{\text{loss,new}}) \cdot x \left[\frac{\text{€}}{\text{kWh}} \right] \quad (2)$$

Figure 20 illustrates the results of this analysis. First, the course of the net present value for a nominal power $P_{nom} = 3600$ kW and an calculative interest rate $i = 0,05$ is calculated. However, the net present value only becomes positive after twelve years, which is why the nominal power is reduced to $P_{nom} = 3200$ kW for the further investigations. At reduced nominal power, an average efficiency of 97.68 % is achieved, leading to an annual loss energy of ca. 330 MWh. The net present value of this investment crosses zero after nine years, assuming an calculative interest rate of $i = 0,05$. To determine the impact of the interest rate on the results, the calculation is repeated for $i = 0$ and $i = 0.1$. For $i = 0$ the net present value turns positive after seven years. Hence, if there was no other opportunity to invest the money, needed in addition to increase the nominal power from 1800 kW to 3200 kW, and inflation rates are disregarded, this investment would be compensated after seven years. Seven years is the minimum time

Figure 20: Net present value of investments for different DC-DC converter systems with various nominal powers for varying interest rates.

Table 3: Nominal power and average efficiency of the MV-LV connection.

Grid Node	Nominal Power of DC-DC Converters	Average Efficiency MVDC-LVDC	Nominal Power of AFEs	Nominal Power of Transformers	Average Efficiency MVAC-LVDC
IT-center	3.2 MW	97.68 %	3.2 MW	2 MVA	97.72 %
Energy Center	1.8 MW	96.71 %	1.8 MW	2 MVA	95.79 %
P1	600 kW	93.84 %	600 kW	630 kVA	95.2 %
P2	400 kW	93.70 %	400 kW	630 kVA	95.27 %
P3	600 kW	93.93 %	600 kW	630 kVA	95.29 %
P5	400 kW	93.75 %	400 kW	630 kVA	95.3 %

span after which the investment becomes beneficial, assuming that there are no negative interest rates. On the other hand, an increased interest rate of $i = 0.1$ postpones the positive net present value to between thirteen to fourteen years. As investment for the $P_{nom} = 3200$ kW configuration has proven to be advantageous compared to the configuration for the highest efficiency possible, and provides enough spare parts to guarantee (n-1) security, this configuration is chosen for all further investigations.

4.2 Cable Transmission Losses

As the next step, cable transmission losses for different DC grid voltages and grid configurations are compared to the three-phase AC reference grid with an effective line-to-ground-voltage of $U_{LE} = \frac{10}{\sqrt{3}}$ kV. In order to choose a suitable cable cross section, the maximum nominal load

current is determined using the aforementioned power flow calculation tools. Then, a corresponding cable cross section is selected according to (VDE, DIN, 2018) and the transmission losses are determined by another iteration of the power-flow calculation with updated cable parameters. If the voltage at any grid node drops below 90 % of the nominal voltage, the cable cross section increases and the algorithm iterates one more time. Also, if the the maximum rated current was overcome parallel lines would be chosen. An overview of the resulting cable cross sections and maximum nominal currents per cable are listed in Table 4. The necessity of having parallel lines is either mentioned in the first column, or indicated in the second column by "(p)", for the substations scenarios, where they are required. While in the AC-reference case a three-phase cable system and supply only via one substation (Sub1) is considered, the analysis of the DC systems investigates bipolar and monopolar grid configurations and the numbers of substations supplying the Campus west area varies between one and three.

Table 4: Cable cross sections and resulting maximum current per cable.

Grid Voltage and Configuration	Cross Section [mm ²] 1 sub 3 subs	max. nominal current per cable [A] 1 sub 3 subs
10 kV AC	150	191
8 kV bipolar	150 150	207 133
7 kV bipolar	150 150	236 152
6 kV bipolar	150 150	276 178
5 kV bipolar	185 150	331 213
3 kV bipolar	500 185	554 356
2,5 kV bipolar	185(p) 300	333 428
1,5 kV bipolar, with parallel lines	500 240	561 359
5 kV monopolar	185(p) 300	332 427
3 kV monopolar, with parallel lines	500 240	556 357

Figure 21 shows that for most nominal voltages and grid configurations, cable transmission using DC technology is more efficient than using AC technology. The results for the DC scenarios consist of three different groups. The groups differentiate between the number of active substations that supply the Campus West MV grid with power from the surrounding public AC grid. The substations are located as indicated by Figure 1 in Section 2. Having more than one substation to supply the grid reduces the maximum nominal current to which the cable cross section is chosen accordingly. A reduced current due to a greater number of active substations, or due to an increased grid voltage leads to reduced transmission losses. Except for the cases in which the reduced maximum nominal current allows for a smaller cable cross section. Under these circumstances, the smaller cable cross section is chosen so that it reduces material consumption and thus, investment costs, but may also lead to increased transmission losses. In addition, Figure 21 points out that increasing the number of active substations from two to three has no significant effect on the transmission losses. This can be explained by considering the location of the substations Sub2 and Sub3. While Sub2 is located in the middle of the Campus West area, close to the main power consumers, the energy center and the IT-center, Sub3 is located further away, close to parking house P5. Assuming that there is no power-flow control applied to the substations, the power flow from the substations to the grid nodes is divided according to the ratio of the cable transmission resistances. Hence, Sub3, if active, delivers power

to P5. The transmission length from Sub3 to P5 is rather short and the power demand does not exceed 300 kW, which is why adding Sub3 as active substation to the grid setup makes little difference regarding the cable transmission losses.

Considering the results presented in Figure 21 it can be concluded that for voltage levels above ± 2.5 kV or 5 kV respectively, the efficiency of power transmission is better in the DC systems, than in the AC-reference system. However, combined with the cross section values of the cables from Table 4, it becomes clear, that for voltage levels beneath ± 6 kV, 12 kV respectively, bigger cross sections than in the AC-reference systems and thus, more material, is used. Therefore, DC transmission in the Campus West area is only better regarding efficiency and material consumption for voltage levels above ± 6 kV /12 kV. Starting from that voltage level, monopolar grids would be more advantageous than bipolar grids, because bipolar grids require a neutral conductor and thus consist of minimum three cables. In contrast, the monopolar grids consist solely of a forward conductor and a return conductor leading to decreased material consumption in addition to an increased efficiency compared to the three phase AC-reference grid.

Figure 21: Cable transmission losses for DC-systems with different voltage levels and grid configurations compared to the AC case.

4.3 MV Substation Losses

This subsection analyses the overall system losses, including the losses in the substations at the coupling points from the public AC grid to the private Campus West grid. Figure 22 depicts the total losses of the AC-reference system of one year, which are at circa 540 MWh. The losses in the supplying substation Sub1 consider the losses in a 4 MVA power transformer with a peak efficiency of 0.99532 according to (European Commission, 2014) and the efficiency curve according to Figure 18. The share of the substation losses in the total losses is approximately 13.5 %.

Table 5: Nominal power, average efficiency and resulting losses for three active substations supplying the MVDC grid.

	Sub 1	Sub 2	Sub 3
Losses [MWh]	219	98	5
Average Efficiency	97.8 %	97.5 %	92.4 %
P_{nom}	2.5 MW	1.6 MW	1.6 MW

In contrast, the substation losses that Figure 23 illustrates are approximately at 320 MWh which leads to a share of between 38 % and 43 % depending on the DC grid scenario. The higher losses in the DC substation are caused by the rectification, which is achieved by the 3LNPC converter in this analysis. While the average efficiency of the 4 MVA 50 Hz transformer is at $\eta_{50Hz,4MVA} = 99.51\%$, the additional losses from rectification reduce the average substation efficiency to $\eta_{AC-DC,Sub1} = 97.8\%$. The overall losses for the DC-grid scenarios with one active substation vary between 744 MWh and 797 MWh depending on the voltage level and are circa 200 MWh to 250 MWh greater than the AC reference case. The advantages of DC power transmission identified in the previous subsection cannot compensate the additional losses in the substation caused by rectification.

In a next step, the impact of supplying the DC grid from more than one substations is investigated. As it is discussed in the previous subsection, an increasing number of substations potentially reduces the cable transmission losses. Moreover, as the power supply for Campus West is distributed among the active substations, each substation can be designed for a lower nominal power, which could lead to reduced material consumption. Figure 24 shows the overall losses with three active substations. As can be seen, the overall losses slightly increase compared to the results in Figure 23. This is due to the fact that the power needed to supply the area is divided among three substations, allowing for a smaller design of the equipment. Because each substation is now designed for a smaller nominal power, the operation point of the substation remains similar to the operation point of Sub1, in the cases when only one substation supplies the DC grid. An overview of the corresponding parameters is given in Table 5. It is also noticeable that in either scenario, AC, DC with one active substation, or DC with three active substations, the losses for supplying the IT-center account for the largest share of the total losses. That is because the IT-center consumes constantly a power of 1.6 MW, which makes the losses that occur during power conversion so significant.

As mentioned in Section 2, another advantage of electricity grids based on DC technology is the better power flow control. For the following analysis the power needed to supply Campus West was assumed as equally distributed among the active substations. Figure 25 illustrates the resulting losses in the substations. As can be seen, this form of power flow control does not reduce the substation losses significantly. However, by distributing the power among three active substations, a reduction from 320 MWh to 315 MWh can be achieved. The losses in the substations do not change with increasing grid-voltage, as it is assumed, that the conduction losses, that decrease with declining current, are compensated by higher switching losses and the circumstances that more switching devices might be needed to withstand the higher voltages. However, the equal distribution of the power supply, allows for reduced nominal power of the assets. An overview of the characterising parameters can be taken from Table 6. Moreover, distributing the power to be supplied equally among the active substations, leads to an increase of the cable transmission losses, as is shown in Figure 26. Since the overall losses of all DC grid scenarios under consideration exceed the losses of the AC reference system, the

Figure 22: Overview of the overall losses in the AC system.

Figure 23: Comparison of the system losses for DC systems of different voltage levels and grid configurations.

Figure 24: Comparison of the system losses for DC systems of different voltage levels and grid configurations with three active substations.

Figure 25: Comparison of the MV substation losses for DC systems of different voltage levels and grid configurations with an equally distributed power flow.

Figure 26: Comparison of cable transmission losses of DC systems of different voltage levels and grid configurations with an equally distributed power flow and the AC-reference system.

economic comparison is omitted.

4.4 Impact of increasing Distance

As concluded in the previous subsection, the advantages in efficiency regarding DC power transmission cannot compensate the losses in the AC-DC substations in the Campus West case study. In this section the DC grid concepts are compared again to the AC-reference system. This time the distances between the grid nodes are multiplied by a factor of ten,

Table 6: Nominal power, average efficiency and resulting losses for three active substations supplying the MVDC grid while applying power flow control.

	<i>Sub 1, Sub 2</i>	<i>Sub 1, Sub 2, Sub3</i>
<i>Losses per Sub. [MWh]</i>	160	105
<i>Average Efficiency</i>	97.8 %	97.9 %
<i>P_{nom}</i>	2 MW	1.6 MW

Figure 27: Overview of the energy losses in the AC system for grid node distances increased by factor of 10.

Figure 28: System losses for DC systems using the same cable cross section as the AC-reference system with three active substations and for grid node distances increased by factor of 10.

compared to the cases in the previous subsections. Figure 27 depicts the overall losses in the AC system. The cable losses have now a share of about 57 % of the over all losses (of approximately 1120 MWh). The increase in cable length leads to over all system losses that are twice as high, compared to the case in Figure 22. For comparison, Figure 28 depicts the resulting overall system losses for the DC scenarios where the same cable cross section as in the AC-reference system can be used. With grid node distances ranging from 500 m to 3800 m, the DC grid configurations are by 235 MWh to 300 MWh more efficient than the AC reference grid.

4.5 Variation of 3LNPC Efficiency

For the comparison in the preceding subsection of the MVDC-LVDC and Medium Voltage Alternating Current (MVAC)-LVDC connection points it was assumed that the 3LNPC implemented

Figure 29: Efficiency curve of the low voltage 3LNPC with a maximum efficiency of 97 %.

on the low voltage side has the same maximum efficiency value, as the medium voltage 3LNPC that is used in the medium voltage AC to DC substations, which is $\eta_{max,3LNPC} = 98.5\%$. Depending on the type of switches and diodes that are used in the topology, the maximum efficiency might also be lower. Hence, in the following, the impact of a lower maximum efficiency of the low voltage 3LNPC on the feasibility analysis is investigated. Therefore, the sensitivity of this parameter is evaluated at the example of two different maximum efficiency values, $\eta_{max,1} = 0.97\%$ and $\eta_{max,2} = 0.96\%$. Figure 29 and Figure 30 depict the course of the converter efficiency for different operating points.

Lowering the assumed maximum efficiency to $\eta_{max,1} = 0.97\%$ for the 3LNPC implemented in the MVAC-LVDC interfaces in the AC reference scenario, leads to an increase in the energy losses, as can be seen in Figure 31. The annual loss energy in the MVAC-LVDC interfaces sums up to 680 MWh and exceeds the loss energy in the MVDC-LVDC converters by 268 MWh. As the loss energy in the MVAC-LVDC interfaces needs to be transmitted through the cables and is provided by the substation, the cable transmission losses and the energy losses in the substation increase as well. The resulting overall energy losses add up to 818 MWh and are shown in Figure 32. Even though the energy losses increase in every category, the rise in losses can be mainly attributed to the losses in the IT-center. Despite the fact that the annual loss energy in the AC reference system exceeds the annual losses in the DC system, the net present value of investing in the DC system still results in a negative value after a period of 15 years, as is illustrated by Equation 4. Table 7 lists the parameters used for this net present value analysis and Equation 3 describes the calculation. On the other hand, when $\eta_{max,2} = 0.96\%$ is considered, the total annual loss energy is at 1002 MWh. An overview of the overall losses is shown in Figure 33. A reapplication of Equation 3 results in a positive net present value after nine years. The net present value of the investment after 15 years is shown in Equation 5. For the calculation of the annual energy losses of the DC scenario, the cable transmission losses of the ± 8 kV scenario were used. Considering the cable losses of the other DC scenarios further postpones the point in time where the DC grid scenario becomes feasible.

Considering these results and the findings from Subsection 4.1, it can be concluded that in this example, the feasibility of the DC system is highly dependent on the maximum efficiency values assumed for the converters, as well as the course of the efficiency curves over the range of operation points. As in the example a formerly non-feasible DC system becomes feasible in under ten years, if the maximum efficiency of the DC-DC converters is 1.7% higher than the maximum efficiency of the AC-DC converter.

Figure 30: Efficiency curve of the low voltage 3LNPC with a maximum efficiency of 96 %.

Figure 31: Comparison of the annual energy losses in the MVDC-LVDC and MVAC-LVDC connection points of the 5 kV DC scenario and the 10 kV AC reference scenario.

Figure 32: Energy losses over one year for a low voltage 3LNPC with a maximum efficiency of 97 %.

Table 7: Parameters for the net present value analysis.

	AC Reference Scenario		DC Scenario		
	Pricing		Costs	Costs	
DC-DC Converter	150 €/ kW			7000 kW	1.05 Mio.€
AC-DC Converter	75 €/ kW	7000 kW	0.53 Mio.€	4000 kW	0.3 Mio.€
MV-LV Transformer	25 €/ kW	6520 kVA	0.163 Mio.€		
3-phase Cable 150mm ²	25.3 €/ m	1400 m	0.035 Mio.€		
Cable 150mm ²	8.1 €/ m			3·1400 m	0.034 Mio.€
MV-MV Transformer	25 €/ m	4000 kVA	0.1 Mio.€	4000 kVA	0.1 Mio.€
∑			0.823 Mio.€		1.484 Mio.€
Annual Energy Losses $\eta_{max} = 0.97$	0.405 €/kWh	817.9 MWh	0.331 Mio.€	744.2 MWh	0.301 Mio.€
Annual Energy Losses $\eta_{max} = 0.96$	0.405 €/kWh	1002.3 MWh	0.406 Mio.€	744.2 MWh	0.301 Mio.€

Figure 33: Energy losses over one year for a low voltage 3LNPC with a maximum efficiency of 96 %.

$$NPV_{\eta=97}(t = T) = 0.823 \text{ Mio.€} - 1.484 \text{ Mio.€} + \sum_{t=1}^T \frac{(E_{\text{loss,AC}} - E_{\text{loss,DC}}) \cdot 0.405 \frac{\text{€}}{\text{kWh}}}{(1+i)^t} \quad (3)$$

$$NPV_{\eta=97}(t = 15) = -349610 \text{ €} \quad (4)$$

$$NPV_{\eta=96}(t = 15) = 291606 \text{ €} \quad (5)$$

4.6 Limits and critical review of the analysis

In this subsection the assumptions that this analysis is based on, are critically reviewed and the resulting limitations are explained.

As the case study includes a consumer that withdraws constantly a high amount of power, it could be that the application of the results to other use cases needs to be critically evaluated, especially concerning the derivation of more generalised conclusions.

Depending on the type of switches and diodes that are used in the MVDC-LVDC and MVAC-LVDC interfaces, not only the maximum efficiency, but also the course of the efficiency curve over the range of operation points might vary. As demonstrated in the previous subsection, this has a non negligible impact on the result of the technology comparison and should be further investigated.

The comparison of the cable transmission losses is based on the assumption that the current densities that can be realised without exceeding the thermal limits of the cable are the same for AC and DC transmission. In DC cable systems, the load is mainly distributed among two conductors, while in AC systems the load is distributed among three conductors. Hence, it is very likely that the heat dissipation is increased in DC systems and therefore allows for higher current densities. This could allow for further reduction of material consumption.

Within this analysis only the 3LNPC topology was considered as rectifier in the MVAC-MVDC substations. Since this analysis has shown, that the application of power-flow control has not contributed to a significant increase in overall system efficiency in this particular case study and considering that feeding power back into the public grid is avoided, diode bridge rectifiers

could also be an option. This of course would also necessitate additional costs and space for filters.

5 Conclusions

In the context of this case study different parameters have been identified, that lead to better feasibility of a DC-grid, compared to the AC reference grid scenario. While the impact of the cable transmission losses is comparably low and only becomes relevant when the transmission length is increased, the key influencing factor is the efficiency of the converters used in the grid systems. In the previous chapters it was shown that DC grid scenarios become potentially feasible after nine years or more, if the DC-DC converters connecting the MVDC grid to the LVDC grids have a maximum efficiency that exceeds the efficiency of the active rectifiers in the AC reference scenario by 1.7 %. Also, for the use case investigated in this case study, the efficiency of the MV AFE was identified to have significant impact on the overall system efficiency.

Moreover, the application of power-flow control in the substations allows for smaller transformer and AFE-sizing, but it did not contribute to the reduction of the substation losses. Also, the equal distribution of the system load among the active substations using power-flow control does increase cable transmission losses, as the transmitted power has to travel longer distances. Nevertheless, operating the DC grid with more than one substation and thereby creating meshed grid structures potentially reduces the cable transmission losses.

Further regarding transmission losses, this analysis also showed that selecting the cable cross section while prioritising minimum material consumption, leads to higher losses. And with material consumption and efficiency as criteria, the choice should fall on monopolar grid configurations with a sufficiently high voltage. Within the analysis of Campus West, monopolar grid structures with a grid voltage of $U_{DC} \geq 12$ kV have proven to be advantageous compared to the 10 kV AC reference scenario.

In addition, it was found that oversizing the DC-DC converters in order to achieve a more efficient operating point is financially rewarding for a load that is mainly constant. This is illustrated by the analysis the net present values of converter-systems with different nominal powers to connect the IT-center to the MVDC grid. In this example, the investment in the oversized converter is compensated after seven to twelve years.

Future work should further investigate the modelling of converter efficiency, in order to obtain results that can further differentiate between different types of semiconductor switches or types of converter control. In addition, further considerations should be given to the aspect of material consumption by determining tolerable current densities in DC cable configurations and comparing the material consumption of the medium frequency transformers and 50 Hz transformers implemented in different DC and AC grid configurations.

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